

2nd International Conference on Sustainable Employability
Building Bridges between Science and Practice -
<http://www.employability21.com/>

12-13 September 2018
Provinciehuis Vlaams Brabant, Leuven, Belgium

Aristomenis Kotsakis, Matthias Nübling,
Nikolaos P. Bakas, George Pelekanakis,
John Thanopoulos

Acknowledgement

This work has been partly supported by the
University of Piraeus Research Center.

COPSOQ v.3 ,The Greek Validation Study, a post crisis assessment of the Psychosocial Risks in Greece

Aristomenis Kotsakis, Matthias Nübling,
Nikolaos P. Bakas, George Pelekanakis,
John Thanopoulos

**Greek COPSOQ V.3 VARIABLES,
From an Organizational Change point of view
Post Crisis Restructuring (context-process-impact)**

Influence
Job Attractiveness
Meaning of Work
Arrangements & Procedures
at Work
Quality of Leadership
Trust
Justice
Work Environment
Mobbing
Quantitative Demands
Emotional Demands
Bullying - Threats of Violence
(from Colleagues)
Bullying - Threats of Violence
(from Customers)

Work Life Balance
Job Insecurity
Personal Well Being
Job Satisfaction
(Intention to Leave)
Job Satisfaction Overall
General Health
Burnout
Mental Health

Our approach:

- to analyze a complex system of
- Input – Output Indicators
- with Machine Learning Algorithms

**Greek COPSOQ V.3 Variables,
from an Organizational Change (Restructuring) point of view in the Early Post-Crisis period)**

Influence
 Job Attractiveness
 Meaning of Work
 Arrangements & Procedures
 at Work
 Quality of Leadership
 Trust
 Justice
 Work Environment
 Mobbing
 Quantitative Demands
 Emotional Demands
 Bullying - Threats of Violence
 (from Colleagues)
 Bullying - Threats of Violence
 (from Customers)

Work Life Balance
 Job Insecurity
 Personal Well Being
 Job Satisfaction
 (Intention to Leave)
 Job Satisfaction Overall
 General Health
 Burnout
 Mental Health

- **Early post crisis Input (Restructuring context + process)→Output(Restructuring impact)**
- **Understand the Analysis Mechanism (Statistics, Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence)**
- **If we change CONTEXT, how much and which way it affects any IMPACT?**
- **SORTED Importance of Context Variables to Impacts**
- **=>Interventions Management (evidence based management DECISIONS)**

- **N=1000, Academic, Private-Public Sectors**
- **719 Initial Responses**
- **426 Complete & Valid Observations**
- **19 Features (Risk Variables)**

Data Utilized

**Which is the best Method to analyse the
Employee Experience Feedback database ?**

Basic Analysis

Multiple Correlations

Clustering maps

In Depth Analysis

Linear Regression

Optimal, Higher-order Regression

Deep Neural Networks

k-Nearest Neighbors

Interventions Management

Sensitivity analysis

Conclusions

COPSOQ v.3 ,The Greek Validation Study, a post crisis assessment of the Psychosocial Risks in Greece

Correlations Table	Quantitative Demands	Emotional Demands	Work Life Balance	Influence	Job Attractiveness	Meaning of Work	Arng. Prcnds at Work	Quality of Leadership	Trust	Justice	Work Environment	Job Insecurity	Bullying from Customers	Personal Well Being	Job Stsfctn JSL	Job Stsfctn JSO	General Health	Burnout	Mental Health
Quantitative Demands	1	0.1428	0.4573	0.4456	0.3555	0.2178	0.0505	-0.1135	0.1697	-0.2399	-0.096	-0.2293	0.0739	-0.0132	-0.0809	-0.0664	0.0411	0.2946	0.1954
Emotional Demands	0.1428	1	0.4462	-0.1666	-0.2709	-0.3743	0.1217	-0.3448	-0.1027	-0.3437	0.2172	0.3285	-0.4242	0.4556	-0.3446	-0.3835	0.2587	0.4981	-0.1802
Work Life Balance	0.4573	0.4462	1	0.124	-0.0374	-0.1797	0.0197	-0.3321	-0.0262	-0.3987	0.1359	0.0715	0.123	0.2818	-0.2721	-0.3926	0.2684	0.5735	-0.0979
Influence	0.4456	-0.1666	0.124	1	0.4618	0.4404	0.061	0.1148	0.2337	-0.0264	-0.3256	-0.4176	0.2682	-0.1766	0.1024	0.1384	-0.0519	0.0147	0.2364
Job Attractiveness	0.3555	-0.2709	-0.0374	0.4618	1	0.5605	0.0059	0.1792	0.2255	0.0566	-0.1804	-0.3858	0.3115	-0.2716	0.1894	0.2627	-0.1992	-0.1941	0.3177
Meaning of Work	0.2178	-0.3743	-0.1797	0.4404	0.5605	1	0.1912	0.461	0.3892	0.3728	-0.1913	-0.2442	0.2998	-0.4324	0.4917	0.5812	-0.243	-0.2954	0.5713
Arng. Prcnds at Work	0.0505	0.1217	0.0197	0.061	0.0059	0.1912	1	0.2576	0.2952	0.2842	0.1487	0.0817	-0.1454	0.0894	0.0483	0.177	-0.0348	-0.0069	0.017
Quality of Leadership	-0.1135	-0.3448	-0.3321	0.1148	0.1792	0.461	0.2576	1	0.3687	0.6648	-0.1479	-0.1005	0.1872	-0.2545	0.4016	0.677	-0.1645	-0.3528	0.3437
Trust	0.1697	-0.1027	-0.0262	0.2337	0.2255	0.3892	0.2952	0.3687	1	0.3128	-0.0472	-0.1775	0.0568	-0.238	0.2351	0.3206	-0.0866	-0.1381	0.2685
Justice	-0.2399	-0.3437	-0.3987	-0.0264	0.0566	0.3728	0.2842	0.6648	0.3128	1	-0.0736	-0.0243	0.1653	-0.3451	0.4858	0.7271	-0.2841	-0.492	0.3657
Work Environment	-0.096	0.2172	0.1359	-0.3256	-0.1804	-0.1913	0.1487	-0.1479	-0.0472	-0.0736	1	0.3034	-0.2681	0.2301	-0.1089	-0.265	0.0421	0.0689	-0.1074
Job Insecurity	-0.2293	0.3285	0.0715	-0.4176	-0.3858	-0.2442	0.0817	-0.1005	-0.1775	-0.0243	0.3034	1	-0.2976	0.3299	-0.0798	-0.1439	0.0965	0.1772	-0.0827
Bullying from Customers	0.0739	-0.4242	0.123	0.2682	0.3115	0.2998	-0.1454	0.1872	0.0568	0.1653	-0.2681	-0.2976	1	-0.5673	0.3106	0.2744	-0.1126	-0.2925	0.1862
Personal Well Being	-0.0132	0.4556	0.2818	-0.1766	-0.2716	-0.4324	0.0894	-0.2545	-0.238	-0.3451	0.2301	0.3299	-0.5673	1	-0.4654	-0.4045	0.2749	0.4831	-0.3506
Job Stsfctn JSL	-0.0809	-0.3446	-0.2721	0.1024	0.1894	0.4917	0.0483	0.4016	0.2351	0.4858	-0.1089	-0.0798	0.3106	-0.4654	1	0.5627	-0.2318	-0.4206	0.4389
Job Stsfctn JSO	-0.0664	-0.3835	-0.3926	0.1384	0.2627	0.5812	0.177	0.677	0.3206	0.7271	-0.265	-0.1439	0.2744	-0.4045	0.5627	1	-0.2855	-0.4853	0.309
General Health	0.0411	0.2587	0.2684	-0.0519	-0.1992	-0.243	-0.0348	-0.1645	-0.0866	-0.2841	0.0421	0.0965	-0.1126	0.2749	-0.2318	-0.2855	1	0.4319	-0.2426
Burnout	0.2946	0.4981	0.5735	0.0147	-0.1941	-0.2954	-0.0069	-0.3528	-0.1381	-0.492	0.0689	0.1772	-0.2925	0.4831	-0.4206	-0.4853	0.4319	1	-0.2286
Mental Health	0.1954	-0.1802	-0.0979	0.2364	0.3177	0.5713	0.017	0.3437	0.2685	0.3657	-0.1074	-0.0827	0.1862	-0.3506	0.4389	0.309	-0.2426	-0.2286	1

- Multiple Correlations
- Pairwise all the variables

- N * N pairwise
- Pearson's Correlations Table

Basic Analysis

Multiple Correlations

Clustering maps

In Depth Analysis

Linear Regression

Optimal, Higher-order Regression

Deep Neural Networks

k-Nearest Neighbors

Interventions Management

Sensitivity analysis

Conclusions

COPSOQ v.3 ,The Greek Validation Study, a post crisis assessment of the Psychosocial Risks in Greece

1. $c_{ij} :=$ contingency table (co-occurrence of objects)

2. $s_{ij} :=$ similarity

3. $ds_{ij} := \frac{1}{s_{ij}}$ (dis-similarity)

4. $d_{ij} = \|x_i - x_j\|$ (distance on map)

5. $f_{ij} := |ds_{ij} - d_{ij}|$ (objective function)

6. Optimality criteria satisfied?

↓ YES

NO ↻

Optimization Algorithm

7. End => drawing of the bibliometric map

Clustering Map Constitution Algorithm

The Julia Programming Language

Correlations Map

Threshold (Min. Correlation) to show link = 0.5

Context
Impact

Basic Analysis

Multiple Correlations

Clustering maps

In Depth Analysis

Linear Regression

Optimal, Higher-order Regression

Deep Neural Networks

k-Nearest Neighbors

Interventions Management

Sensitivity analysis

Conclusions

COPSOQ v.3 ,The Greek Validation Study, a post crisis assessment of the Psychosocial Risks in Greece

Basic Analysis

Multiple Correlations

Clustering maps

In Depth Analysis

Linear Regression

**Optimal,
Higher-order
Regression**

Deep Neural Networks

k-Nearest Neighbors

Interventions Management

Sensitivity analysis

Conclusions

COPSOQ v.3 ,The Greek Validation Study, a post crisis assessment of the Psychosocial Risks in Greece

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & F(\mathbf{s}) \\ \text{subject to} \quad & \mathbf{g}_j(\mathbf{s}) \leq 0 \quad j=1, \dots, m \\ & \mathbf{s}_i \in \mathbb{R}^d, \quad i=1, \dots, n \end{aligned}$$

$$f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = a_{0000} + a_{1010}x_1 + a_{1111}x_1^2 + a_{1211}x_1x_2 + \dots$$

- Optimization
- Model Selection

where $F(\mathbf{s})$ and $\mathbf{g}_j(\mathbf{s})$ denote the **objective and constraints** functions respectively, \mathbb{R}^d is a given **set** of **discrete** values, while the **design variables** \mathbf{s}_i ($i=1, \dots, n$) can take values only from this set

In order to investigate combined, multiple correlations among the dependent variable and the independent (candidates), noesys-regression, assumes the following Equation 1, generative non-linear function. Equation 1, continues for all the independent variables, as well as their interactions up to degree 4 (i.e. $x_1x_5x_{11}^3$). However, as only observations/20 variables can be kept in the model, it is needed to select the nonlinear features which are statistically significant (p-value<0.05) and the R² to be maximized. If there exists ten (10) independent candidate variables, then the possible combinations are 2¹⁰=1024 models. If higher order terms of degree two, three or four are included, **the potential models are some trillions or even more**. One solution to this problem is the stepwise regression, however it takes a lot of time to compute, as well as the forward and backward regression does not always converge to the same solution. Hence, noesys-regression, treats this formulation as an **optimization problem**, and a special developed optimizer, performs hundreds or thousands of regression analyses in a limited time space and automatically decides for the optimal model.

$$f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = a_{0000} + a_{1010}x_1 + a_{1111}x_1^2 + a_{1211}x_1x_2 + \dots$$

- 8 dependent variables were used in our model, one per org.change impact.
- The potential regression models for higher order regression, are some trillions or even more
- We treated this as an Optimization problem
- **Reduced the trillions of Regressions to (only!) 10.000 of Regressions**

Computational Complexity

$$Depe - Var = \frac{Var-01 + Var-03^2 + Var-05 * Var-07 + \log(Var-09 + 1) + \sin(Var-11) * \cos(Var-13) * e^{Var-15}}{2}$$

- **Applied Algorithms**
- **Hidden Equation**
- **16 independent Variables**
- **Only 8 exist in model, highly non-linear**
- **Accuracy 99.6%**

Simple Verification Example

Basic Analysis

Multiple Correlations

Clustering maps

In Depth Analysis

Linear Regression

Optimal, Higher-order
Regression

Interventions Management

Sensitivity analysis

Conclusions

Deep Neural Networks

k-Nearest Neighbors

COPSOQ v.3 ,The Greek Validation Study, a post crisis assessment of
the Psychosocial Risks in Greece

- **Circuit of interconnected neurons.**
- **Based on biological neurons**
- **Algorithmic construction, which fall within the area of computational intelligence**
- **Simulate any nonlinear, multivariate relationship.**
- **$g(x)$: sigmoid function**

- **Artificial Neural Networks**
- **Artificial Intelligence**
- **Validation of the results**

$$Y = \sum g(w * x) \quad g(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}$$

Basic Analysis

Multiple Correlations

Clustering maps

In Depth Analysis

Linear Regression

Optimal, Higher-order Regression

Deep Neural Networks

k-Nearest Neighbors

Interventions Management

Sensitivity analysis

Conclusions

COPSOQ v.3 ,The Greek Validation Study, a post crisis assessment of the Psychosocial Risks in Greece

A modified version of the *Profile* method [1, 2] is utilized, in order to investigate each variables contribution to the dependent variable. In particular, each input variable varies within its given (raw) range while all the other input variables are kept constant in a certain value. This constant, takes three discrete values:

- **25% Percentile**
- **Median**
- **75% Percentile**

1. Gevrey, Muriel, Ioannis Dimopoulos, and Sovan Lek. "Review and comparison of methods to study the contribution of variables in artificial neural network models." *Ecological modelling* 160.3 (2003): 249-264.
2. Olden, Julian D., and Donald A. Jackson. "Illuminating the "black box": a randomization approach for understanding variable contributions in artificial neural networks." *Ecological modelling* 154.1-2 (2002): 135-150.

Sensitivity Analysis

The same:

- For each impact
- For each Variable

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =ALL.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Arng_Prcds_at_Work.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Bullying_from_Customers.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Burnout.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Emotional_Demands.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =General_Health.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Influence.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Job_Attractiveness.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Job_Insecurity.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Job_Stsfcn_JSL.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Job_Stsfcn_JSJ.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Justice.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Meaning_of_Work.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Personal_Well_Being.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Quality_of_Leadership.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Quantitative_Demands.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Trust.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Work_Environment.jpeg

sensitivity_y=Mental_Health_x =Work_Life_Balance.jpeg

All Graphs for Mental Health Summarize Importance in A simple graph

4 Non-linear Methods

Averaged Importance

Importances for Mental_Health

Which are the actual Associations ?

Context/Impact Status

Context	Impact
Influence	Work Life Balance
Job Attractiveness	Job Insecurity
Meaning of Work	Personal Well Being
Arrangements & Procedures at Work	Job Satisfaction (Intention to Leave)
Quality of Leadership	Job Satisfaction Overall
Trust	General Health
Justice	Burnout
Work Environment	Mental Health
Mobbing	
Quantitative Demands	
Emotional Demands	
Bullying - Threats of Violence (from Colleagues)	
Bullying - Threats of Violence (from Customers)	

IMPACT VS CONTEXT

Correlations Map

Context
Impact

Work life Balance

Job Insecurity

Personal Well being

Job Satisfaction JSL

Job Satisfaction JSO

General Health

Burnout

Mental Health

- Sensitivity for all Impacts
- Corresponding Map

Basic Analysis

Multiple Correlations

Clustering maps

In Depth Analysis

Linear Regression

Optimal, Higher-order Regression

Deep Neural Networks

k-Nearest Neighbors

Interventions Management

Sensitivity analysis

Conclusions

COPSOQ v.3 ,The Greek Validation Study, a post crisis assessment of the Psychosocial Risks in Greece

Our Contribution: a unified, self validating **Framework** of Analysis

- Four Regression Methods
 - Linear
 - Higher Order
 - Neural Networks
 - K-Nearest Neighbors
- Three interpretation stages
 - Sensitivity Analysis (deep)
 - Summarized Sensitivities (intermediate)
 - Correlations Map (shallow)
- Comparisons

Conclusions

- **Quantitative demands** is a **significant predictor** for **Work Life Balance**
- **Influence** has strongly **negative correlation** with **Job insecurity**
- **Meaning of work** highly associated with **Intension to Leave**
- **Justice** and **Quality of Leadership** affects **Job Satisfaction (JSO)**
- **Lack of Justice**, also, **negative impact** to **General Health**
- **Lack of Trust & Bullying from Customers** major **negative impact** to **Personal well being**
- **Trust** highly affects decreasingly, **Burnout**
- **Trust**, also **contributes** to **Mental Health**

Conclusions

COPSOQ v.3 ,The Greek Validation Study, a post crisis assessment of the Psychosocial Risks in Greece

Aristomenis Kotsakis, Matthias Nübling,
Nikolaos P. Bakas, George Pelekanakis,
John Thanopoulos, Greece